

THE INCORPORATION OF INDIGENOUS TECHNOLOGY INTO THE TEACHING OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN SCHOOL CONTEXT: TRANSFORMING EDUCATION FOR A CHANGING WORLD

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Abstract

Under its third aim, to appreciate the interaction between people's values, technology, society, and the environment, the South African Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) technology Grades R–9 includes indigenous technology, and the sub-aim emphasizes that students learn how indigenous cultures use specific materials and processes to satisfy needs and become aware of indigenous intellectual property rights. This suggests that technology teachers should incorporate locally produced technology into their lessons, which they currently do not. In order to better understand how technology teachers perceive and attempt to incorporate indigenous technology into their lessons, this qualitative interpretive study was conducted. At all levels, it should be applied to incorporate indigenous technology into the teaching of technology in South African schools. In the Free State Province's Motheo district, seven technology teachers for grade 7 were conveniently chosen to take part in the study. The results show that although technology teachers are familiar with local technology, they find it difficult to incorporate it into their lessons.

Keywords: understanding; incorporate; indigenous technology; curriculum; indigenous

1. INTRODUCTION

The 2014 Inter-Agency Support Group on Indigenous Issues of the United Nations is dedicated to valuing indigenous knowledge for sustainable development.

Teaching about indigenous knowledge, in this case, indigenous technology is considered the primary method of ensuring this sustainability. Therefore, rather than focusing solely on western technology, technology teachers should incorporate indigenous technology into their lessons. The South African Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS), which incorporates indigenous knowledge systems, attests to attempts to indigenize education made there since 1994 (Department of Basic Education [DBE] 2011, 10). However, it is hardly ever attempted by technology teachers to include indigenous technology in their lessons (Williams and Gumbo, 2012). Therefore, it is important to investigate how technology teachers perceive and attempt to use indigenous technology in their lessons. In this article, "technology" refers to the academic discipline of technology or technology education, not to educational technology.

Rural areas have a lot of indigenous technology, like several in the South African province of Free State, but technology lecturers don't use it to make the subject applicable to the area. Contrary to CAPS technology. In addition to indigenous technology, learners are constantly exposed to Western epistemologies that they can hardly understand (Shipp, 2013). Failure to recognize the importance of indigenous technology is the equivalent of giving in to historical amnesia (Rains 1999), depriving students of the chance to learn about indigenous technology. According to Mudaly and Ismail (2013), curricula should consider indigenous knowledge's comprehensive, pluralistic, and redemptive interpretations of human experience. This demands curriculum indigenization in addition to transformational measures in South Africa.

Education is made relevant to the worldviews of the students when the curriculum and teaching methods are indigenous. Teaching students about indigenous engineering, food production, processing, textiles, etc. can increase their engagement in the classroom (Gumbo, 2003). It is not enough to say that indigenous students should see reflections of themselves, their cultures, their histories, and their communities on the walls and corridors of their schools (Shipp, 2013). There also needs to be evidence of indigenous knowledge in the lessons that are designed and taught to the learners. Learning about indigenous technology is beneficial for both indigenous and non-indigenous learners. A learning sequence concerning a narrative is described in a study by two teachers at Broome Secondary School in Australia by Bevan and Shillinglaw (2010). Indigenous students were questioned about a story's meaning at the beginning of the tale. Family, law, truth, and country were among the responses given by the learners. However, the comments from the non-indigenous students included items like entertainment, literature, and works of fiction. This demonstrates how different cultural worldviews have different knowledge sources and formats, which can deepen learners' comprehension as they discover one another cultures. Given the foregoing, the following research question is put forth: What knowledge about and efforts are made to include indigenous technology in lessons by technology teachers?

The following is a list of the sub-questions:

- What sources of technology are recognized by technology teachers?
- What does indigenous technology from these sources mean to technology teachers?
- How do these teachers try to use locally produced technology in their lessons?

The definitions of indigenous technology and indigenous learners are then given, followed by a discussion of the technology curriculum and teaching, a brief justification for the chosen theoretical framework, the study's methodologies, and its conclusions and discussion. Then, pertinent judgments and suggestions are made.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Indigenous Technology

Because it is more useful, indigenous knowledge may be regarded as technology. (Grenier, 2002 & Robyn, 2002). There are initiatives to incorporate local technologies into CAPS that are minimal and superficial. The following is the third goal of technology: "Appreciate the relationships among values and attitudes of people, technology, society, and the environment" (DBE, 2011, 10). This goal states, in part: "Whenever feasible, learners." should be made aware of the various knowledge systems that coexist. They ought to learn how indigenous societies have adapted particular techniques and materials to meet requirements and learn about indigenous peoples' rights to intellectual property (DBE, 2011, 10). When referring to indigenous technology, the words "where possible," "made aware," "become aware," and "have used" are superficial. Educating students about local technology is inadequate and gives the sense that native technology was only present in the past. Additionally, teachers that strive to include indigenous knowledge in their classes and instruction receive little assistance (Mudaly & Ismail, 2013).

The technology comprises the intricate disciplines of technological designs and apparatuses, such as looms, fabrics, and other handcrafted items (Hoppers, 2001). According to Cheek (1992), technology is a body of knowledge that culture has created on how to manage the environment, extract resources, manufacture commodities, and services, and enhance the quality of life. According to Ogunbure (2011: 87), any technology inside a social praxis is a product of culture. This statement lends support to the cultural perspective of technology. In this view, culture encompasses human manifestations that use technology as a processing and delivery tool, both material and non-material (Obikeze, 2011; Ogunbure, 2011). Technology is categorized by Obikeze (2011) into separate categories into commodities and services such as material products, social goods or services, and intellectual goods. It further divides these categories into social,

social goods or services, and communication technologies. According to Ogunbure (2011), technology is a component of intelligence and education. This definition of technology aids in making it applicable to indigenous situations.

The traditional definition of technology is "the use of information, skills, attitudes, and resources to satisfy human needs and desires by creating workable solutions to issues while taking social and environmental considerations" (DBE, 2011, 8). The International Technology and Engineering Educators Association (ITEEA, 2011: 15) defines technology as how individuals change the natural world to fit their own purpose, which is similar to Western definitions. In general, it refers to the wide range of techniques and information that people employ to enhance human potential and meet their needs and desires. These definitions only encompass technology's tangible components, as opposed to Obikeze's (2011) and Ogunbure's (2011) definitions, which also include technology's intangible components.

Indigenous people can be used to define indigenous learners. Coates (2004) claims that although indigenous people are not socially static, they have kept their cultural practices, ancestors' affiliations and values, oral histories, and strong, multigenerational relationships to the land, rituals, and cultural pursuits. The majority of indigenous people participate in the decolonization and re-indigenization processes; one recent example is student demonstrations at South African colleges against Western-dominated curricula. Most of these pupils were Black. Considering this, this concept refers to historically marginalized individuals, the majority of whom are Black.

2.2 Technology Education and Curriculum

Technology approaches and technology education are criticized for relying on the Western conceptions of science and epistemologies (Volmink, 1998 and Williams, 2000) It is a prevalent misconception that technology is an ancient science. 1997). The outcomes revealed that in a poll carried out by Dugger (2008) in the United States in 2001 59% of interviewees thought science and technology were interchangeable. Once more 62% of the same study from 2004 added to this viewpoint. Science in the West is more than non-Western knowledge, making it a phenomenon that affects everyone to the rejection of unconventional knowledge. The design model guiding technology education is a version of the scientific inquiry paradigm, i.e., identify the issue/need/want, research, come up with potential solutions, make, share, and assess. It pushes the fluidity of indigenous peoples' problem-solving methods into a linear design mould.

Williams (2000) contends that the reductionist role of science is a crucial component of it and makes use of the more recent field of technology. It even misrepresents how technology is actually used in the real world (Williams, 2000). Williams (2000 & Gumbo: 49) contend that in indigenous cultures, learners create a method as they advance toward task fulfilment.

Therefore, it is essential to incorporate indigenous ideas into education rather than sticking solely to Western dominant approaches. Therefore, studying indigenous technology can aid in directing the curriculum and instruction in a way that recognizes and celebrates the technology used by indigenous people. The creativity that is influenced by learners' cultural worldviews is constrained when their thinking is framed within a predetermined model. Because the result of a design or solution incorporates more factors than can be captured in a series of process steps, technology is more than the accomplishment of a set of process processes (Williams, 2000).

The examples above demonstrate that students bring "teknnowledgé" and skills they have learned from elders or subject-matter experts in their communities to the technology class. To ensure that students have a deep understanding of the subject, it is crucial that technology lecturers approach their lessons from an indigenous perspective. According to Mavhunga (2008), incorporating indigenous knowledge into the curriculum will increase its relevance and students' conceptual grasp. According to Zengeya-Makuku et al. (2013), teaching from an indigenous viewpoint links students' knowledge from their homes with what they learn in school. Demmert (2001) asserts that teachers should encourage students to investigate fundamental concepts that are ingrained in the culturally pertinent information and tasks and to engage in authentic and purposeful problem-solving.

3. THE THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The community cultural wealth idea is used to frame the investigation (CCW). CCW upholds democratic ideals by valuing the viewpoints and expertise of indigenous people and supporting and recognizing the information that students bring to the classroom from their surroundings (Moloi, 2013 and Yosso, 2005).

CCW is appropriate for this research because it recognizes the richness of indigenous technology and Gumbo's recommendation that it be used in instruction. According to Yosso (2005) and Yosso and Garca (2007), CCW is based on aspirational, linguistic, social, navigational, family, and resistance capitals.

The community's capacity to endure and maintain its aspirations for the future in the face of setbacks and obstacles is known as aspirational capital. Despite the difficulties in incorporating indigenous technology, learners' aspirations should be represented through technology. Linguistic capital describes the variety of language and communication skills that learners have acquired from their societies, such as facial expression, memory, attention to detail, and storytelling abilities. Language is a potent means of expressing culture, and it is full of deep meaning, some of which are even difficult to translate. Therefore, it is crucial that learners master essential technological ideas in their native tongues as well.

Social capital is the relationships among networks of individuals in a society as its citizens benefit from one another's knowledge and experience. They share information, abilities, and resources in order to help one another both practically and emotionally. As a result, incorporating indigenous technology gives learners the chance to learn and comprehend the subject from one another's surroundings. The cultural information that exists inside and between families and friends is known as familial capital. It preserves a healthy relationship between the community and its resources, serving as an example of how to care for others and make provisions. It also possesses a sense of collective history, memory, and cultural intuition.

Teachers can encourage a sense of community among learners who will study technology as a group from an Ubuntu perspective. The concept of navigational capital refers to the inherent abilities and resources acquired without necessarily attending formal institutions, which are the skills required navigating social organizations. The knowledge and abilities that are developed through oppositional behaviour that challenges inequity is referred to as resistant capital. The rich information that technology learners have from their backgrounds can be encouraged to come to light and fight concerns of unfair treatment.

It is clear that CCW is consistent with culturally relevant pedagogy, which emphasizes incorporating learners' past knowledge, experiences from their homes and communities, and background knowledge into classroom instruction (Gumbo, 2016; Ladson-Billings, 2000). It recognizes that every learner has a unique learning process that is influenced by their backgrounds, languages, families, and social or cultural identities. This implies that while they learn about technology, learners might develop their ability to co-create meaning. As a result, the technology practices used in indigenous cultures offer a plethora of information to help learners make learning more meaningful (Gumbo, 2017). Such a plethora of information should be known to technology teachers, who should include it in their lessons.

4. ANALYSIS METHODS

This study is based on an indigenous research paradigm that rejects using information and people as mere research objects (Wilson, 2001). Because the issue at hand concerns the rebirth of indigenous technology, this paradigm was chosen. Because of its purpose—that is, to attempt to understand the lived experiences of individuals and to establish the everyday meanings of occurrences in their lives, thoughts, and ideas, the study adopted an interpretive methodology (Lowenberg, 1993 in Wu & Chen, 2005). The interpretation of the participating teachers' grasp of indigenous technology and attempts to incorporate it into their lessons and instruction was therefore made easier by the design. Geertz (1973) asserts that what we term our data are really our own creations of other people's constructions of what they and their compatriots are up to. According to Walsham (2006, 320), teachers and students are exposed to indigenous technology that is available in the Free State and that they can fully utilize.

In order to protect their identities, even Grade 7 technology teachers who attended the Mathematics, Science, and Technology (MST) professional development workshops in Botshabelo in June 2017 participated in this study under the pseudonyms Tt1, Tt2, Tt3, etc., where Tt stands for "technology teacher." The MST Academy organized the workshops. The three components of Walsham's (2006) three-part data collection strategy; choosing a style of involvement; getting and sustaining access and gathering field data were implemented. The researcher called the teachers to introduce himself, explain the aim of the study and request their participation. We spoke with each teacher for around ten minutes on the phone to build a relationship and eliminate the distance barrier, even attempting to speak in their native tongue (Sesotho) This was carried out until seven teachers were located who were willing to take part. In indigenous cultures, taking the time to introduce oneself is an appreciated greeting.

By including the facilitator of the technology workshop in the selection of the teachers, direct interaction with

the participants was avoided during the data-gathering stage. This was done for several reasons, including encouraging teachers to be open and honest about the topic under investigation and to gain a new perspective on the topic from the viewpoint of the participants. The facilitator received a brief introduction to the study's recruitment process. Throughout the workshop sessions, he spoke with the instructors. Therefore, teachers who volunteered were chosen using a convenient selection method. The list of instructors who were willing to volunteer was then emailed to him along with their contact details. Free State DBE authorized the investigation.

Most interpretive studies use interviews as a tool to access the interpretations of informants in the field (Walsham, 2006: 323). Thus, structured interviews with the teachers were organized. The teachers who agreed to participate in the study should get a handbook for open-ended interviews from a facilitator. The facilitator received the interview guide and was instructed to print it and provide it to the teachers for completion. An introduction, the goal of the study, and an explanation of ethics were all included in the guide. According to the interview guide, the participants had to discuss their knowledge of indigenous technology, the value of incorporating it into technology, the sources of indigenous technology in the environments in which they teach, and how they would go about planning a lesson that incorporates indigenous technology. Teachers were permitted to explain the ideas in their native tongue and then provide the English translation. Finally, teachers had to create a lesson plan that incorporates indigenous technology and were organized according to its objectives, concepts, content, teaching methodologies, resources, and method of evaluation.

The completed interview guide was posted by the facilitator. There was no need to transcribe the data because the teachers provided their responses by filling out the interview guide. Smith and Osborn's interpretive phenomenological analysis (IPA) was used to analyze the data (2004). The teachers' responses to the questions served as the basis for the analysis. Briefly put, IPA entails the following steps:

- transcribe data by methodically searching for themes through data coding.
- develop master themes by making connections in the data.
- identify sub-themes within the master themes.
- and translate master themes and their sub-themes into a narrative account supported by verbatim extracts from the participants.

The teachers' lessons were subjected to document analysis. The analysis looked at the subject and the content, right down to the resources and evaluation, to see if any indigenous technology had been used. By accurately describing the research outcomes as the data's sources, using peer review and discussion (with MST Academy) to strengthen and explain the meaning's veracity, and adhering to the IPA framework, the data's reliability was secured.

5. FINDINGS

5.1 Expressed Knowledge of Indigenous Technology by Teachers

By categorizing key concepts that the teachers used to define indigenous technology and using the language they used to support those notions, data analysis revealed the teachers' comprehension of this technology.

- Traditional/historical/local/intergenerational: Skills, knowledge, and resources; local decision-making; local approaches and materials; bodies of knowledge, skills, teaching, and beliefs of local people; conventional systems used in communities. knowledge of a group of people residing in a specific area; that which local people know or believe in.
- Informal knowledge: African knowledge systems from ancient times that were not formally acknowledged or recorded in books and did not require formal education.
- Technology: A means of transferring knowledge and skills that is integrated with
- other subjects; theories that were applied to solve practical issues; technology that ancestors employed in the past to craft and manufacture necessary items from gold and metals; practical knowledge imparted to the young, such as the making of mortar and pestles by boys' and girls' decorations using various colours, textures, and beads; native tools and methods; and goods made without the use of references or following rules and procedures but producing good results.

The sources (or locations) that the teachers connected technology to are shown in Table 1. The blank

spaces signify that the teachers omitted any source citations. The teachers were free to use either English or Sesotho to communicate technologically.

Indigenous technology	Source
Lelwala (stone for grinding peanuts to make peanut butter)	
Sekele (hoe for ploughing)	
Clay pot	Clay pot
Spear	Iron
Grain storage	Community
Strengthening techniques	Community
Crushing grains	Community
Paola (heating)	Community
Tools	Stones
Refrigerator	Underground holes, clay
Communication	Signs, drawings
Reed baskets	Reed

Table 1. Examples of indigenous technologies and sources

5.2 The Significance of Incorporating Indigenous Technology into Technology Education

The results are given in accordance with the topics that surfaced from this question.

5.2.1 Using Indigenous Technology to Understand

According to the teachers, outdated technology can be used as a tool to help learners better grasp technology. Regarding this, "children must comprehend that indigenous technology offers a chance to generate creative concepts from current ideas" (Tt3). According to Tt1, indigenous technology is more inexpensive than Western technological systems. Tt5 asserts that "learners have some background information" about the accomplishments and actions of their ancestors, which can aid them in comprehending how procedures were carried out in the past and present. Because some technology is practiced at home, students can understand it better (Tt7). The teachers were adamant that students should be aware of how previous generations lived, ate, and dressed. According to Tt6, for instance, "it is necessary for the learners to compare and know how indigenous techniques and current technology and processes are related and how they differ." Tt6 gave an illustration: "Meat was processed into biltong by exposing it to the sun with a little salt."

5.2.2 Indigenous Technology's Relevance to Learners' Learning

The results showed that because "it contains the topics which the learners can relate to," indigenous technology should be incorporated into students' learning (Tt5). The educators believed that native technology would make educational technology meaningful to students. "We must acknowledge our way of

life and relate the skills and information gained by our ancestors as a way of survival and development of their lives," according to Tt11 explicitly. Indigenous technology, according to Tt9, is crucial because it helps students learn what they already know. The learners may learn about "caring for nature" because native people live so close to the natural world (Tt10).

5.2.3 The Technology, Skills, and Resource Contribution of Indigenous People

The lecturers made strong arguments about how indigenous people contribute to technology, saying things like, "We are also innovative, informed, and intellectual because people in the past had the skills and knowledge to employ various resources to meet our requirements. They could build clay pots out of clay, light fire by pressing stones together, utilize animal skin for clothing, and smelt iron to make spears (Tt4). White people "believe that everything is from them, yet it belongs to us, the crank and cams," according to Tt2's opinion.

6. DISCUSSION

The teachers have an understanding of indigenous technology based on their cultural setting in Africa. Their definitions are consistent with those that have been taken into account in the literature and are pertinent to native technology and culture. They recognized the close relationship between technology and culture, the importance of technology for sustainable development, and the wealth of indigenous technology that may be obtained, particularly from the elders (Robyn, 2002; Mudaly and Ismail, 2013; Obikeze, 2011; and Ogunbure, 2011). The most frequent sources of the technologies mentioned above are noted to be the community. This has significant ramifications for how technology is taught. For instance, according to Gumbo (2016) and Ladson-Billings (2000), both elders and professionals in specific technological sectors can be seen as providers of technological knowledge, and they can even give teachers advice about culturally relevant education.

Indigenous technology was described by the teachers as being casual and archaic. This perspective may be influenced by the DBE (2011)'s limitations on indigenous technologies from the past. Because of this idea, teachers might not take indigenous technology seriously. The use of indigenous technology in agriculture, art, architecture, games, and other fields should be emphasized. Indigenous technology is dynamic and pervasive; it can be seen, especially in rural settings. Scholars like Mudaly and Ismail (2013), Rains (1999), and Shipp oppose limiting it to the past (2013). It should also be disregarded that urban areas lack indigenous technology; urban schools should also incorporate it.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated how Grade 7 technology instructors saw technology and made an effort to include it into their lessons. The emphasis that teachers place on technology and their knowledge of it can change how technology is taught and give students a deeper grasp of it. First, questions regarding the definition and significance of indigenous technology were posed to the teachers. Additionally, they were required to name its sources. The study's conclusions demonstrate that although teachers are aware of indigenous technology, they tend to interpret it historically. The teachers have trouble incorporating native technology into their lessons.

The following recommendations are made:

- The DBE should reconsider CAPS' cursory incorporation of indigenous technology and its restriction to the past because it hinders technological comprehension and puts indigenous technology in jeopardy.
- Let training in incorporating local technology be a part of technology teachers' professional development.
- Technologies educators should: broaden their knowledge of contemporary indigenous technology.
- gather technological expertise, particularly from local elders, to contextualize technology and give it significance to students.
- place significance on culturally relevant teaching methods rather than viewing them as obstacles.

7.1 An Idea for Teaching Technology in an Indigenous Manner

Design methodologies, communication skills, mechanical systems and control, and investigative techniques are all included under the umbrella word "content." Extend the definition of technology as a teacher to

incorporate the viewpoint of the indigenous people. Adapt the inventive designs to the contexts of the students. Instead, of relying solely on conventional talents, gather graphic design expertise from indigenous contexts. Investigate culturally appropriate teaching strategies. Improve students' ability to communicate ideas by using an oral presentation, which is the most common form of communication among indigenous people. Profit from the fact that students are giving oral presentations of their research by exploring technology use in that context, such as YouTube. Explain the technological concepts in relation to the regional contexts, for example, how to lever systems are used to load materials into granaries and pull water from a pit, or devices that ring a bell to announce the beginning of a religious service. The ultimate goal of technology education is to equip students for both urban employment and jobs in native surroundings.

This paper significantly advances technology teachers' knowledge of indigenous technology and the concept of its incorporation into the teaching of technology.

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